

Supplementary Figure S1. A best scoring Maximum Likelihood tree based on ITS rDNA region showing relationships of *Trichophyton spiraliforme* sp. nov. and *Trichophyton persicum* sp. nov. to other dermatophytes belonging to the *T. benhamiae* complex. Ex-type isolates are designated by a superscript T. *Trichophyton rubrum* CBS 202.88 was used as the outgroup.